

The Essential Oil from the Flowerheads of *Perovskia Atriplicifolia*. Benth.

BY

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The essential oil from *Perovskia atriplicifolia*, Benth, does not appear to have been examined before. *P. atriplicifolia* occurs in Western Tibet, in Afghanistan and Baluchistan at altitudes of 7,500 to 10,200 feet (Hooker's *Flora*). The samples used were kindly sent by the Political Agent, Kurram, Parachinar, N. W. F. Province and were identified by Mr. R. N. Parker, the Forest Botanist of this Institute.

The samples were distilled on a semi-large scale at this Institute. Only flowerheads were used; these were steam distilled at a pressure of 40 lbs. and a dark green oil with a strong camphoraceous odour was obtained. The yield of oil was 1.0 per cent. on the weight of air-dried flowerheads. Stalks were found to give a similar oil but the yield of oil was only 0.2 per cent.

When the oil had been dried by anhydrous magnesium sulphate and filtered, it had a light olive-green

colour, and had the following constants: d_{30}^{20} 0.8943; n_D^{30} 1.4748; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 8.53^\circ$, acid value 0.2; ester value, 30.4; ester value, after acetylation, 49.22. These values for ester, before and after acetylation, appear to indicate an ester content of 10.8 per cent. and of free alcohol 5.4 per cent. in the oil.

A preliminary examination of the oil showed that it was free from aldehydes and ketones and that it consists of about 50 per cent. of terpenes among which *d*-pinene, β -pinene and camphene have been definitely identified, 15-18 per cent. of alcohols and esters consisting mainly of *d*-borneol and bornyl acetate, and the rest of sesquiterpenes consisting mainly of α -caryophyllene and aromadendrene. The combined acids were found to consist almost entirely of acetic acid, no other acids having been discovered. Tests for cineol have so far given negative results although the higher fractions among the terpene fraction have a very strong odour of eucalyptus.

As a source of *d*-borneol this oil would seem to be of interest, and of some economic importance, particularly in view of the fact that camphene is also present in the oil; but this will largely depend on the quantity of material available. The necessary data regarding the occurrence and maximum output of the flowerheads of *P. atriplicifolia* are not within the scope of this paper. *d*-Borneol has been known to occur in the oil of the Borneo camphor tree (Schimmel's Report, 1913, 33), and in *Callitris calcarata* and *C. Glauca* (Baker and Smith, *A Research on the Pines of Australia*).

Systematic repeated fractionations of the bulk oil at 200 mm. pressure using a four pear still-head gave the following fractions:—

Fraction	B. p.	Yield.	Sp. gravity.	Ref. index.	Rotation.	Analysis	
						C	H
I	120-125°	4.3 per cent.	0.8604	1.4611	+11.16	88.0	11.9
II	125-130°	20.0 per cent.	0.8683	1.4630	+12.93	87.7	11.9
III	130-135°	7.1 per cent.	0.8756	1.4634	+15.45	85.1	11.2
IV	135-140°	8.2 per cent.	0.8802	1.4640	+17.66	83.2	11.5
V	140-145°	8.0 per cent.	0.9072	1.4640	+20.01	81.3	11.3
		47.6 per cent.					
VI	155-160°	2.6 per cent.					
VII	165-175°	10.2 per cent.	0.9383	1.4705	+10.95	75.2	10.5
VIII	175-185°	2.5 per cent.					
		1.8 per cent.					
IX	185-190°	16.5 per cent.					
		6.5 per cent.					
X	200-210°	6.5 per cent.	0.9078	1.4970	-1.06	87.7	11.8
XI	210-220°	21.7 per cent.	0.9221	1.5012	+1.02	87.9	11.8
		28.2 per cent.					

(The use of the fourpear still-head was discontinued while distilling fractions above 190°).

Fractions I-V consisted mainly of the terpenes: Fraction I had the familiar smell of pinene and fractions IV and V had the strong smell of cineol. As the density of all these fractions was high, they were suspected to contain traces of borneol or bornyl acetate, and were therefore refractionated over sodium at the ordinary pressure of 700 mm. The following new fractions were thus obtained.

Fraction.	B. p.	Yield.	Sp. gr.	Ref. index.	Rotation.	Analysis	
						O	H
I	154-156°	1.1 per cent.	0.8580	1.4620	+12.31	88.2	11.8
II	156-160°	5.2 per cent.	0.8606	1.4625	+12.9	87.8	11.9
III	160-164°	6.7 per cent.	0.8646	1.4629	+14.6	87.9	11.8
IV	164-168°	6.2 per cent.	0.8688	1.4630	+15.0	87.5	11.8
V	168-172°	8.5 per cent.	0.8734	1.4630	+16.9	85.0	11.3
VI	172-180°	3.0 per cent.	0.8750	1.4640	+15.3		

Fraction I consists mainly of *d*- α -pinene, which gives a good yield of the nitrosochloride; this when recrystallised from cold chloroform and methyl alcohol crystallised in fine white needles m. p. 109° (with decomposition). The nitrol piperidine crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 118°. Pinene nitrosochloride was obtained from fractions II and III so that these fractions also contained α -pinene. β -Pinene and camphene were absent in fraction I. Fraction II consists of *d*- α -pinene, camphene and a little β -pinene. Camphene was identified by hydrating this fraction with acetic acid-sulphuric acid solution and hydrolysing the oil so obtained with alcoholic potash. *iso*-Borneol, b. p. 210-215°/700 mm., was obtained. This when recrystallised from light petroleum crystallised in snow white flakes m. p. 209-210° (in sealed tube). β -Pinene was identified by oxidising fraction II with dilute ice-cold permanganate in caustic soda solution and working up the oxidation products in the usual manner, when a little sparingly soluble sodium salt of nopinic acid was obtained, from which on acidifying and extracting with benzene, nopinic acid crystallising in prismatic needles were obtained. These when recrystallised from hot water gave the pure acid m. p. 126-127°. A mixture with nopinic acid made from pure pinene was unaltered in melting point.

Fraction III consists mainly of β -pinene, a little camphene and a little pinene. This fraction gave a good yield of pinic acid.

Fraction IV contains β -pinene mainly, camphene being absent. Fraction V and VI had a strong smell of cineol but these fractions gave no phosphoric acid compound. Tests for limonene were negative. Phellandrene is possible as a small trace of a nitrosite was obtained. These fractions are still under examination.

Fraction VII on distilling gave a small quantity of *d*-borneol (1.0 per cent.). Fractions VI to IX consisted of esters and alcohols. These were mixed together and saponified with alcoholic potash and the alcohol so obtained was repeatedly fractionated, the borneol fractions being congealed in ice and rapidly filtered each time. In this manner 8.5 per cent. of *d*-borneol was obtained. This was found to be free from camphor, as on treating its alcoholic solution with aqueous solution of semicarbazide acetate, no semicarbazone was obtained.

d-Borneol b. p. 210°/700 mm. had the following constants when crystallised from light petroleum: m. p. 200-201°; Sp. gr., 1.008; rotation in alcohol, +34.5°; analysis, C=78.0; H=11.8.

After separation of the *d*-borneol from the fraction of b. p. 200-220°/700 mm. the saponified oil gave the following fractions:

Fraction.	B. p.	Yield.	Sp. gr.	Ref. index.	Rotation.
(A)	170-180°/700 mm.	4.3 per cent.	0.8760	1.4640	+15.8
(B)	180-185° "	1.0 "	—	1.4658	+16.0
(C)	185-195° "	1.2 "	0.9282	1.4670	—
(D)	200-220° "	3.0 "	0.9303	1.4730	+13.4

These alcohols are still under examination. Fraction (A) from its constants would appear to be mainly a hydrocarbon.

Fractions X and XI were found to consist mainly of sesquiterpenes. These were fractionated over sodium and the following main fractions were obtained :

Frac- tion	B. p.	Yield (per cent.)	Sp. gr.	Ref. index.	Rota- tion.	Analysis.	
						C	H
(a)	125-130°/5 mm. or 255-260°/700 mm.	16.6	0.9078	1.4970	-1.06	87.8	11.8
(b)	130-135°/5 mm. or 260-262°/700 mm.	4.1	0.9109	1.4978	-0.76	88.1	11.8

No sesquiterpene alcohol was present. Both these sesquiterpene fractions gave all the colour reactions of aromadendrene (Baker and Smith, "A Research on the Eucalyptus and their Essential Oils," p. 416). Thus an acetic acid solution or a chloroform solution of the oil gave a purple colour when a very dilute solution of bromine in acetic acid was added: this purple colour develops to an indigo blue. Phosphoric acid also gave a light crimson colour, so did concentrated hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid when each of these was added separately to the acetic acid solution or chloroform solution of the sesquiterpene. Colour reactions for cadinene were negative. α -Caryophyllene was identified in both the above fractions, as they each gave a fair yield of nitrosochloride, m. p. 164-165°. This when recrystallised from cold chloroform and methyl alcohol gave prisms m. p. 179° (with decomp.). The corresponding nitrol piperide crystallises from alcohol, m. p. 145° (Wallach and Tuttle quote m. p. 143° for α -caryophyllene nitrol piperide). The other derivatives of α -caryophyllene are being prepared for confirmation.

The combined acids were found to consist only of acetic acid. The alkaline solution obtained from the saponification of the esters was rendered free of oil and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and steam distilled and the distillate was collected in fractions.

Fraction I. 0.3347 Ag-salt gave $\text{Ag} = 0.2166$.

Found: $\text{Ag} = 64.73$ per cent.

Fraction II. 0.2784 Ag-salt gave $\text{Ag} = 0.1762$.

Found: $\text{Ag} = 63.3$ per cent.

Fraction III. 0.4114 Ag-salt gave $\text{Ag} = 0.2661$.

Found: $\text{Ag} = 64.7$ per cent.

CH_3COOAg requires $\text{Ag} = 64.6$ per cent.

No other acids, either volatile or non-volatile in steam, could be detected.

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